

Deliverable D2.3

Guidelines for molecular characterization of gene edited material

31st of July, 2025

Document Control Sheet

PROJECT INFORMATION

Project Number	101061015	
Project Acronym	GeneBEcon	
Project Full title	Capturing the potential of Gene editing for a sustainable BioEconomy	
Project Start Date	1 September 2022	
Project Duration	36 months	
Funding Instrument	Horizon Europe	Funding Scheme Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01	

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Deliverable No	D2.3
Deliverable Title	Molecular characterization of gene edited material
Work-Package No	WP2
Work-Package Title	Advancing NGTs in biobased R&I
WP-Leader (Name and Short Org. Name)	Katrijn Van Laere (EV-ILVO)
Task No	T2.4
Task Title	Genomic analysis of gene edited material
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Reviewers (Name and Short Org. Name)	
Status	Draft <input type="checkbox"/> Final <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Deliverable Type	Report <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Data <input type="checkbox"/> Demonstration <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/>
Dissemination Level	Public (PU) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sensitive (SEN) <input type="checkbox"/> Classified <input type="checkbox"/>
Date Approved by Coordinator	

DOCUMENT VERSION HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Description of Change
V1	18/07/2025	Elke Vereecke and Katrijn Van Laere (EV-ILVO)	Finishing the first draft of the document
V2	25/07/2025	Tom Ruttink (EV-ILVO)	Finishing the second draft of the document
V3	30/07/2025	Elke Vereecke and Katrijn Van Laere (EV-ILVO)	Finishing the third/final version of the document

DOCUMENT REVIEW

Reviewer	Date	Reviewer Name (Short Organisation Name)
1	24/07/2025	Per Hofvander (SLU)
2	25/07/2025	Matias Gonzalez (SLU)

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
CRISPR/Cas	Clustered Regulatory Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats/CRISPR-associated protein
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
gRNA	Guide RNA (ribonucleic acid)
NGT	New Genomic Techniques
GMO	Genetically Modified Organism
EURL	European Union Reference Laboratories
GE	Gene Editing
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
NGS	New Generation Sequencing
EPPO	European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organisation
RA	risk assessment
HTS	High Throughput Sequencing
DBS	Double Strand Break
NHEJ	Non-Homologous End Joining
HDR	homology-directed repair
DRT	DNA Repair Template
RNP	Ribonucleoprotein
PCR	Polymerase Chain Reaction
WGS	Whole Genome Shotgun Sequencing
PE	Prime Editing
BE	Base Editing
LOF	Loss of Function
ORF	Open Reading Frame
SNP	Single Nucleotide Polymorphism
FN	False Negative
FP	False Positive
PAM	Protospacer Adjacent Motif
ZEP	Zeaxanthin epoxidase
VDE	Violaxanthin de-epoxidase
VDL	Violaxanthin de-epoxidase-like
GBSS	Granule Bound Starch Synthase
SS	Soluble Starch Synthase
PVY	Potato Virus Y
PacBio	Pacific Biosciences
ONT	Oxford Nanopore Technology
SMRT	Single Molecule Real-Time sequencing
CFU	Colony-Forming Unit
KO	Knockout
ICE	Inference of CRISPR edits
TIDE	Tracking of Indels by DEcomposition
PEG	Polyethylene Glycol

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1. About the GeneBEcon Project

GeneBEcon - capturing the potential of Gene editing for a sustainable BioEconomy

GeneBEcon is an ambitious Horizon Europe-funded project, which examines the innovation potential of gene editing to enable a sustainable bioeconomy in Europe. Through the application of this technology in potato and microalgae, GeneBEcon intends to promote energy-efficient, low-input, and zero-pollution agricultural production and clean industrial processing.

New Genomic Techniques (NGTs) represent a powerful toolbox which is complementary to traditional breeding techniques and contributes to alleviating current pressing challenges such as pollution and climate change. However, these techniques do not yet reach their full potential in Europe. GeneBEcon will advance research and innovation, acting on two fronts: through new gene editing developments at the technological level, as well as considering social, economic, and regulatory dimensions.

Among NGTs, gene editing holds the greatest potential for contributing to the ambitious objectives of the European Green Deal, the 2030 Climate Target Plan, and the Circular Economy Action Plan. Nonetheless, risks and benefits must be assessed to ensure that gene editing innovations, just like any other type of innovation, are developed in a responsible, inclusive, and transparent way. GeneBEcon aims to address these concerns and propel Europe towards a cleaner, more sustainable and zero-pollution agricultural and industrial production.

GeneBEcon will construct a toolbox for gene editing using potato and microalgae as case studies and it will assess regulatory options in terms of data requirements for risk assessment, analyse the economic impact and consider societal perceptions. The gene-edited potato will be virus-resistant to enable reduced use of pesticides in potato cultivation, and it will produce a higher quality starch allowing a more environmentally friendly potato starch processing saving up to 75,000 tonnes of chemicals and 7.5 GWh of energy in the EU every year. Likewise, gene-edited microalgae will allow resource-efficient and clean production of industrially relevant compounds and the repurposing of microalgae residual biomass as animal feed. GeneBEcon has a budget of 5.5 million Euros and a duration of three years as of 1 September, 2022. GeneBEcon is executed by a multidisciplinary consortium with leading scientists from 11 European countries and in interdisciplinary collaboration with stakeholders.

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2. Executive Summary

Molecular characterization of gene edited genotypes is not optional, it is central in the life cycle of a gene edited (GE) event and must be adapted to the gene editing strategy used. This report provides a practical and comprehensive framework for the molecular characterization of GE plants using CRISPR/Cas technology. The guidelines are intended to support developers, researchers, and regulators in generating reliable, high-quality data for detailed molecular characterization of GE genotypes. The generated molecular data can also be used in the context of risk assessment (RA), regulatory approval, and public transparency. Gene editing via CRISPR/Cas offers a precise, efficient, and flexible tool to address challenges in agriculture and industrial biotechnology. Yet, regulatory approval of New Genomic Techniques (NGTs) in the EU still requires careful and detailed molecular characterization, both under the current legislation for genetically modified organisms (GMO) and the evolving NGT legislative proposal. The guidelines presented here are therefore essential for preparing dossiers that meet the expectations of the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), the European Union Reference Laboratories (EURLs), and national competent authorities.

The document outlines the full life cycle of a gene editing event, including the (1) selection of plant material and CRISPR strategy, (2) the identification and sequencing of on-target and off-target loci, (3) the use of high-throughput sequencing (HTS) platforms for mutation detection, (4) the functional interpretation of mutations (e.g., loss-of-function analysis), (5) the comparative analysis of edited and non-edited genotypes, and (6) the preparation of regulatory documentation and support for RA. The GeneBEwise toolbox (<https://genebewise.genebecon.eu/>) supports all stages from gRNA design to data interpretation.

HTS technologies are indispensable tools for capturing the full scope of genome edits with high precision. Technical recommendations are provided to ensure accuracy, reproducibility, and traceability of molecular HTS data. This includes laboratory and IT infrastructure requirements, quality control standards and personnel qualifications, mitigation strategies for false positive/negative detection, and alignment with existing diagnostic standards from EPPO and EFSA. The report emphasizes that **molecular characterization must distinguish between mutated and reference (non-mutated) alleles both at the on-target sites and the predicted off-target sites. False positives/negatives must be minimized through strict laboratory protocols and validated bioinformatics pipelines.**

To demonstrate practical application, the report includes **two case studies**:

1. A CRISPR-edited microalga (*Nannochloropsis*) engineered to enhance carotenoid production (zeaxanthin and violaxanthin), with careful design of the gRNA to minimize off-target effects.
2. A CRISPR-edited potato, modified for improved starch quality through a stepwise approach combining non-homologous end joining (NHEJ) and homology-directed repair (HDR), including insertion of a native promoter to increase gene expression in tubers.

These examples illustrate how the provided guidelines can be tailored to different organisms, editing objectives, and regulatory pathways.

By following these guidelines, gene editing developers can ensure their work **meets the scientific and regulatory standards required for safe, sustainable, and socially acceptable innovation** in agriculture and bioeconomy and contribute to public trust, risk communication and effective regulation.

3. Introduction

CRISPR/Cas gene editing has become a powerful tool in plant functional genomics and plant breeding research, offering great potential for the targeted improvement of desired heritable traits [1]. This technique enables precise control (i.e., predictability) over the genomic location to which genome editing is targeted, and, depending on the applied CRISPR strategy, over the editing outcome, thus representing a major advancement over random mutagenesis and transgenics. More specifically, the editing outcome can be of various mutation types (insertion, deletion and/or substitution). The predictability of the editing outcome is dependent on the repair mechanism used and its inherent error profile. The predictability of the genome position where genome editing can be expected depends on the specificity of the CRISPR/Cas enzyme in combination with the sequence similarity between the gRNA and the genomic DNA sequence. To understand the impact of the introduced mutations at molecular and functional levels, detailed characterization of the edited alleles is essential.

Molecular characterization involves the detailed analysis of the edited alleles at nucleotide level using DNA-based technologies in combination with bioinformatic analyses. By assessing the mutated DNA sequences, gene structural features, expression patterns of the mRNA transcript and/or activity of the encoded proteins, the functional impact of the mutations can be predicted. Such comprehensive molecular analysis is essential for RA and regulatory evaluation of CRISPR-edited plants or NGT-derived plants in the frame of authorisation for commercial release.

At the time of writing this report, NGT-derived plants are regulated by the GMO Directives 2001/18/EC, 1829/2003/EC and 1830/2003/EC [2,3,4]. Consequently, if RA is required for NGT plants and their derived products, they are also based on the RA procedures currently applied to (transgenic) GMOs using validated characterization methods endorsed by the EURLs that compare the GMO with their non-GMO comparators. **In the case of NGT-derived plants, we consider the mutated alleles as the equivalent of the GMO event and the pool of available wild-type alleles at the original genomic loci as the equivalent of the non-GMO comparator.**

However, there are increasing concerns that the current legislative framework is not fit for purpose when it comes to NGT-derived plants and that it requires adaptation to keep pace with scientific and technological progress. Within the GeneBEcon project, six alternative regulatory options have been analysed and described [5]. These options include a legal “status quo” scenario, as well as “product-based” and “case-by-case” regulatory approaches (Addendum 2). One of the options, *i.e.*, “option 3”, is comparable to the legislative proposal [6] put forward by the EU commission on July 5th, 2023, which is currently under discussion in the EU trilogues.

Both the current GMO-based legislation and the NGT legislative proposal require a comprehensive molecular characterization of NGT-derived plants. Under the current GMO-based legislation, molecular characterization data (1) supports RA, and (2) is a prerequisite for the development of detection and identification techniques to ensure traceability and labelling prior to regulatory approval and release [7]. In contrast, in the NGT legislative proposal, molecular characterization data is essential to (1) demonstrate that the plant material is an NGT plant and does not contain any genetic material originating from outside the breeders’ gene pool, and (2) distinguish NGT1 and NGT2 plants, where the NGT1 plant meets the criteria set out in annex I of the proposal [6; Addendum 3].

In this report, guidelines are provided for detailed molecular characterization of mutated alleles in regenerated individual plants or *in vitro* plantlets obtained after CRISPR/Cas action. These guidelines can be used during the preparation of an application for regulatory approval of a novel GE event. The guidelines include DNA-based tools and data analysis pipelines for

detecting and characterizing all mutation types, and for comparing mutant alleles with reference (non-mutated) alleles in the comparators, covering edits at both on-target and predictable off-target genome locations. For these guidelines, the considered NGT technology to create GE events is CRISPR/Cas. All guidelines aim to provide recommendations to ensure the reliable use of DNA-based and bioinformatics technologies. In developing these guidelines, existing documents from EFSA on the molecular characterization of GMO plants were considered [8, 9, 10, 11]. However, not all elements from these guidelines are directly applicable to NGT-derived plants. The molecular characterization strategies differ fundamentally. In the case of transgenes, molecular analysis focuses on identifying the introduced DNA fragment(s) and determining all genomic insertion sites and the consequences of the introduction of (foreign) DNA into those genomic locations (i.e., disruption of genes encoded in the sequences flanking the GMO insert). In contrast, for NGT-derived plants, the focus lies on identifying all (target) genomic locations where the Cas enzyme may have acted and verifying whether mutations have occurred at those sites. This distinction requires a tailored approach to molecular analysis and data interpretation in the context of NGTs. In addition to the guidelines for characterization of GMO events, we also looked for parallels in the use of NGS technologies in the frame of pathogen and pest diagnostics, because there the purpose is to detect specific DNA or RNA sequences known to originate from genomic sources (organisms) that need to be monitored. Guidelines for the reliable and correct use of NGS technologies for plant diagnostics have recently been created by a large network of researchers united in the European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organisation (EPPO).

The structure of the report is visualized in Figure 1. We first outline the life cycle of a GE event (section 4) from conception by design and creation of potential mutants, through screening and selection of a candidate GE event, via molecular characterization of alleles at predicted on-target and off-target loci, establishing which alleles are indeed mutated by CRISPR/Cas, interpreting the effects of these mutations on genes and plant phenotypes in the frame of RA, market approval, and post-release monitoring. Then, in section 5, we focus on the type of molecular data that is gathered during the life cycle of a GE event. Section 6 then points on some important similarities and differences between molecular characterization approaches for GE and (transgenic) GMO events. In section 7, we highlight technical guidelines for obtaining high quality data for molecular characterization of GE event, drawing parallels between existing guidelines from the GMO regulations and from the guidelines on using HTS technologies in the frame of plant pathogen and pest diagnostics. Finally in section 8, we show the practical application of several guidelines using case studies from the GeneBEcon project. These cases involve *Nannochloropsis* microalgae engineered for enhanced production of carotenoids (zeaxanthin and violaxanthin) as high-value compounds, and CRISPR-edited potato genotypes, where CRISPR/Cas was used to edit genes involved in starch quality.

Figure 1: Overview of the different sections that will be discussed in this document, together with how they are linked to each other.

4. Overview of the life cycle of a gene editing event

Select starting material, candidate gene and design CRISPR assay

Choice of CRISPR method

- NHEJ
- HDR
- Base editing
- Prime editing

PRE-CHARACTERIZATION PHASE

Create list of alleles per locus in reference genotype

Create candidate CRISPR-edited lines

1

Molecular screen of the collection of regenerants

- Multimeric?
- ♦ Regenerant 1
 - iii) Regenerant 2
 - o) Regenerant 3
 - iii) Regenerant 4
 - iii) Regenerant 5

Select a candidate CRISPR-edited event (plant material)

@ Regenerant 3

SCREENING PHASE

Detailed sequence analysis of selected candidate event at on-target and off-target loci

MOLECULAR CHARACTERIZATION PHASE

Identify CRISPR-induced mutant alleles

IDENTIFICATION PHASE

Identify CRISPR-induced mutant alleles

Place mutant alleles in genome context, and predict protein sequence and function of the protein

10

Functional interpretation per mutated allele

f.e., induced mutation in promoter region led to increased gene expression

Risk assessment

Post-approval market monitoring and enforcement

REGULATORY PHASE

Strategies and bioinformatics pipelines for this step are available in the GeneBEwise toolbox in panel 1 (<https://genebewise.genebecon.eu/>). This information is then used to design highly specific gRNAs, taking the desired on-target versus off-target specificity into account. Strategies to design proper gRNAs are available in the GeneBEwise toolbox in panel 2 (<https://genebewise.genebecon.eu/>). Subsequently, a final list is created detailing each gRNA target and its flanking genomic regions at both on-target and predicted off-target loci, including a sequence length that allows to discriminate between loci and alleles per locus (Figure 3).

Step 3. Create candidate CRISPR-edited genotypes: After identification of target genes and the design of specific gRNAs, a transfection method should be chosen and applied to deliver the CRISPR/Cas components into the reference material. The appropriate transfection method depends both on the plant starting material (protoplasts, explants, single cells, etc.) and the delivery vehicle (plasmid DNA, ribonucleoprotein (RNP), *Agrobacterium* binary vector, etc.) that is used. An overview of the different methods are outlined in Figure 4. CRISPR delivery can be done using physical methods (biolistics, electroporation), chemical treatment (Polyethylene Glycol (PEG)-mediated), or biological means (*Agrobacterium*-mediated).

Figure 4: Overview of the different starting materials, delivery vehicles and transfection methods used in plants, including the advantages (green) and disadvantages (red) for each transfection method.

Protocols for these different transfection methods and regeneration can be consulted in the GeneBEwise toolbox panel 3 (<https://genebewise.genebecon.eu/>). During *in vitro* plant tissue culture and plant regeneration, changes may occur in the plant genome, known as somaclonal variation. Genomic sequence variation created in this way is not regulated by EU legislation, and we therefore also consider the genome changes that result from *in vitro* culture *per se* (i.e. somaclonal variation) as independent from CRISPR/Cas action, and not the subject of risk assessment for GE events.

Step 4. Molecular screen of the collection of regenerants: The molecular screening at this stage focuses on confirming the presence of intended (on-target) mutations in the regenerated plant genotypes. Depending on the objective, both single and stacked on-target mutations (i.e., combinations of GE events at multiple genome locations) may be selected. A variety of screening methods are available to detect CRISPR/Cas-induced mutations (Figure 5). These methods differ in their detection principles, ranging from physical properties of amplified alleles to sequencing-based approaches, and may employ either targeted or untargeted strategies. Targeted screening focuses on specific genomic regions, such as predicted editing sites, and can involve techniques like PCR, restriction enzyme digestion, or amplicon sequencing. Untargeted approaches, such as whole-genome sequencing (WGS) or long-read RNA sequencing (RNA-Seq), provide a broader, unbiased view of the genome or transcriptome. Screening methods also vary in throughput and level of automation, depending on the extent of locus and/or sample multiplexing. In principle, any standard molecular screening technique capable of distinguishing DNA sequence variants (alleles) can be adapted to screen for CRISPR-induced mutations. Many screening methods are only capable of detecting whether a mutation is present or not, while sequencing-based methods are needed to report the actual DNA sequence change itself.

Figure 5: Overview of different CRISPR strategies and their expected outcomes. The top panel illustrates gene editing approaches including NHEJ, HDR using a donor repair template (DRT), and base or prime editing. The bottom panel shows detection methods for identifying the resulting mutations, including PCR-based genotyping and sequencing methods.

Step 5. Select a candidate event (plant material): After the initial general molecular screening of the regenerants, the most promising GE events showing the desired on-target mutations are selected for further detailed molecular and phenotypic characterization.

Step 6. Detailed sequence analysis of selected candidate event(s) at on-target and off-target loci: For the selected candidate GE events HTS-based methods should be used to analyse the mutant alleles at the nucleotide level, both at the intended on-target loci as on the unintended (off-target) loci. Mutations at off-target loci may be predicted based on in silico analysis of sequence similarity between the gRNA target and the genome sequence of the experimental (reference) material. Here, the availability of sequence data for the target locus and other loci with high similarity to the wild-type, to-be-mutated alleles is crucial. HTS yield targeted resequencing data that can be analyzed via bioinformatics tools. Every sequenced allele is compared to the reference genome, allowing for the detection of any combination of insertion, deletion, or substitution. In HTS data any mutation can be detected that results from an edit in the primary DNA sequence in each window if the read length spans the mutated allele. In the GeneBEwise toolbox panel 4 more information and protocols are available for sequence analysis (<https://genebewise.genebecon.eu/>).

Step 7. Create list of alleles per locus in candidate event and compare to reference genotype: The detailed sequence analysis at on-target and off-target loci allows for the creation of a list of alleles and compare these to the reference, non-mutated alleles. For each allele, it is tested whether it is present in the reference material (not edited) or not present in the reference allele set (potentially edited).

Step 8. Identify CRISPR-induced mutant alleles: In a direct comparison between the alleles at gRNA target loci of original reference material and edited material, the presence of alternative alleles at gRNA target sites in the candidate GE event can be interpreted as being derived from CRISPR/Cas action. Each alternative allele is interpreted in the context of the CRISPR/Cas method (NHEJ, PE, BE, HDR), the expected cut site (gRNA binding sequence) and repair mechanism, to evaluate whether the change in sequence can be caused by the respective CRISPR/Cas action, the repair mechanism and inherent error profile, hence expected editing outcome (insertion, deletion, substitution).

Step 9. Place mutant alleles in genome context and estimate effect on encoded protein sequence: Different mutation types can be induced, typically in the range of (short) deletions, insertions, or substitutions. By replacing a segment of the original reference gene sequence by the observed mutated sequence, and evaluation of the upstream and downstream splicing sites, translation initiation codon, open reading frame (ORF), and translation termination codon, the effect of the mutation on the encoded protein sequence can be determined.

Step 10. Functional interpretation per mutated allele: After CRISPR/Cas application the original reference protein may no longer be produced (frameshift mutation of nonsense mutation), or proteins can be identical to the original reference protein (silent mutation), etc. (Figure 6). Mutations in a gene that result in a non-functional protein encoded by that gene are called loss-of-function (LOF) mutations and occur when the ORF downstream of the mutation is disrupted and covers an essential part of the amino acid sequence. BE enables to create a specific point mutation that may result (by design) in a single amino acid change in the protein sequence, a disrupted START codon, premature STOP codon or altered splicing sites. Combined with knowledge of critical residues of the protein sequence, it can be estimated whether that change in amino acid sequence changes the function or activity of the protein. In polyploid species, also the dosage of the mutated alleles need to be taken into consideration to interpret the impact of the CRISPR/Cas application on the protein activity and function.

Figure 6: Figure showing the effect of different DNA mutations on the protein function.

Step 11. Risk assessment and approval: NGT plants are currently regulated by the GMO directives 2001/18/EC, 1829/2003/EC and 1830/2003/EC [2, 3, 4]. Consequently, an RA strategy should be followed for NGT plants and derived food and feed using EURL validated methods to compare the GMO with their non-GMO comparators (Addendum 1). However, the data requirements are not always fit for purpose for NGTs. Within the GeneBEcon project, six different alternative regulatory options are determined and analyzed [5], including a legal “status quo” scenario and more “product-based” and “case-by-case” scenarios (Addendum 2). One of the options, *i.e.*, “option 3”, is similar to the NGT legislative proposal from the EU Commission launched on July 5th, 2023, and which is currently under discussion in the EU trilogues. However, also for regulation according to the legislative proposal or one of the GeneBEcon options, an appropriate molecular characterization of the mutated alleles will be essential for approval.

Step 12. Post-approval market monitoring and enforcement: Under the current GMO legislation, detection, identification, and quantification methods to trace the GMO events (using an event-specific molecular assay) throughout the value chain are essential to endorse enforcement by testing if products on the market are in line with GMO labelling requirements. It is currently under debate whether and how labelling and traceability regulations can be implemented for CRISPR/Cas-derived GE events based on analytical detection methods. It is beyond the scope of this report to provide guidelines for post-approval market monitoring for the presence of potential GE events, based on analytical evidence of sequence variants in materials of unknown origin. While technically it may be possible to determine the allele composition at any given locus, it will likely not be possible to conclude unambiguously that a given sequence variant can only be derived from CRISPR/Cas action, and that therefore the

material tested contains a CRISPR/Cas-derived GE event, and is not a naturally occurring sequence variant. This is for sure the case for NHEJ and BE, which are most commonly applied.

5. Overview of molecular data gathered during subsequent steps in the life cycle of a GE event

Various steps within the life cycle of a GE event (section 4) generate molecular data that contribute to the overall scope of this report, namely the detailed sequence analysis of a selected candidate event at on-target and predictable off-target loci and to determine alleles before versus after CRISPR/Cas mediated mutation. In this section 5, the molecular data generated in preceding steps will be highlighted, with a particular focus on the data relevant and necessary for achieving the scope, as well as those required under EFSA documentation for GMO approval (Addendum 1), the NGT legislative proposal [6] and the six regulatory options described in (Addendum 2).

5.1 Pre-characterization phase: CRISPR design and generation of a CRISPR/Cas GE event

Depending on the choices made in this step, several key pieces of molecular information are defined. The availability of a genome reference depends on the selected plant starting material (reference genotypes), which is essential for downstream sequence analysis. Attention is also given to the existing allelic variation within the chosen reference genotype, as this natural variation must be known prior to gRNA design. The gRNA design determines the specific on-target site in the genome and enables identification of potential unintended off-target sites, as these share high sequence similarity with the on-target site. This information allows for the creation of a detailed overview of allelic variation at the on-target locus and predicted off-target loci in the reference genotype. More information on the bioinformatic pipelines used to identify potential off-target sites can be found in the GeneBEwise toolbox (<https://genebewise.genebecon.eu/>). This reference genotype serves as the so-called "non-GMO comparator" foreseen in GMO legislation, against which CRISPR-edited genotypes will later be assessed. This comparison has to be made knowing that natural variation in the breeders' gene pool and somaclonal variation is hard to exclude or distinguish. Additionally, selecting the CRISPR strategy allows for a preliminary prediction of the expected mutation type. The actual creation of the CRISPR-edited genotypes, which follows this step, will also determine the choice of transformation method and the type of CRISPR delivery system used, whether plasmid-based or RNP-based. These choices have direct implications for the molecular characterization process. For example, when plasmid DNA is used, there may be a need to assess whether any plasmid-derived sequences have been unintentionally integrated into the genome, requiring additional screening steps.

The GeneBEwise toolbox (<https://genebewise.genebecon.eu/>) can be used as a guide to support these decisions. The decisions made within this step will also be required for documentation and reporting to regulatory authorities, as information on the recipient plant is required in terms of complete name (family, genus, species, subspecies, cultivar, strain) and geographical distribution (EFSA Nr. 1) as well as a general description of the trait(s) and characteristics which have been introduced or modified (EFSA Nr. 14 and Nr. 15), related to the candidate gene and CRISPR strategy selected. This information is necessary for EFSA documentation for GMO approval, the NGT legislative proposal, and the regulatory options outlined in [5, 12]. Specifically for the GMO legislation and options 1, 2, 3, 5 and 6, additional information must be provided on the genetic transformation, for example, the method that is used, the plasmids/RNPs that are used, etc. (EFSA Nr. 5, 6, 7, 8, 12, 13). An overview of the data that needs to be given in an EFSA dossier and the possible translation to NGTs is given in Addendum 1.

5.2 Screening phase: Molecular analysis of regenerants and selection of candidate GE event.

In this phase, regenerated plants are screened to identify individuals carrying the intended CRISPR-induced mutation. While this step does not generate new molecular data for characterization, it is crucial to select a plant genotype, referred to as the candidate GE event, that will be followed throughout the remainder of the GE life cycle. The decision made here defines the material from which molecular characterization data will later be obtained. In some cases, the molecular screening method used in this phase already detects the mutations at the target loci (and characterizes them at the nucleotide level), for instance through multiplex amplicon sequencing of all target loci and comparison of sequenced GE alleles to the reference alleles.

5.3 Molecular characterization phase: Detailed sequence analysis of selected candidate GE event at on-target and off-target loci

In this phase, detailed molecular data is generated for the selected candidate event. The focus is on precisely characterizing the CRISPR-induced mutations at the on-target sites, as well as identifying any unintended mutations at predicted off-target loci. This involves the use of DNA-based HTS methods (section 7). The data produced includes the exact DNA sequences at both the on-target and predicted off-target loci, allowing for a clear determination of whether edits have occurred and, if so, their precise nature. For each of these loci, the allelic composition is also established, indicating whether all, some, or none of the reference alleles carry the mutation.

For this part, the molecular characterization requirements described by EFSA for GMO approval must be adapted to fit a GE event. In the case of GMOs, EFSA requires sequence information of both the 5' and 3' flanking regions at each insertion site to assess, among other things, whether any known genes have been disrupted (EFSA Nr. 19) [9]. For GE events, this principle can be translated to the requirement for sequence information of both the 5' and 3' flanking regions at the gRNA target site, as well as at other regions of the genome with high sequence similarity to the gRNA target site (i.e., predicted off-target sites), at which CRISPR/Cas activity can reasonably be expected. Therefore, the DNA sequence data generated in this phase serves to fulfill the first part of these regulatory requirements. In a subsequent step, these sequence data must be placed back into the genome context to determine whether any known gene or regulatory element has been affected, and what the predicted effect is of the mutation on gene expression or protein functionality. Regulatory options 1, 2, and 6 (Addendum 2) also require sequence information on the on-target site and predicted off-target sites as described above.

Other EFSA requirements for GMO characterization include determining the size and copy number of all detectable inserts (complete and partial), the organization of inserted genetic material at each insertion site, and subcellular location(s) of the insert(s) (EFSA Nr. 16, 17, 18, and 20). For CRISPR/Cas events relying on NHEJ, these requirements generally do not apply, as no foreign DNA is inserted. Only in rare occasions transfection vector segments (i.e., foreign DNA) jump into the DSB during NHEJ. Also, when using HDR or PE, a DNA repair template may be introduced. In those cases, EFSA's requirements can be addressed by identifying possible Cas cut sites (based on gRNA sequence and Protospacer Adjacent Motif (PAM) presence) and assessing where and how many times the repair template has been integrated into the genome. This assessment is also needed for regulatory options 1, 2, 3, 5, 6 (Addendum 2).

Under the NGT legislative proposal, NGT plants are categorized as NGT1 or NGT2. NGT1 requires a verification process, while NGT2 requires an authorization procedure similar to that

for GMOs, but with an adapted RA. NGT1 plants are considered equivalent to conventionally bred plants if they meet the criteria set out in Annex I of the legislative proposal (Addendum 3). In short, NGT1 plants may contain up to 20 specific genetic modifications within DNA sequences that share similarity with the targeted site and can be predicted using bioinformatic tools. In other words, it should be demonstrated by molecular characterization tools that no more than 20 specific genetic modifications are present at the on-target and predicted off-target loci, at which CRISPR/Cas activity can be predicted. It also has to be shown that insertions and substitutions also exist within the breeders' gene pool. The molecular data gathered during this phase supports the assessment of whether the requirements for classification as NGT1 are met. If these requirements are met, the verification process concludes and the results are submitted to the competent authority of the Member State. If the requirements are not met, the plant is classified as NGT2, in which case the molecular data gathered will be used for the adapted risk assessment, as outlined in the GMO legislation above.

5.4 Interpretation phase: comparative list of alleles and estimation of effect on gene function

In this phase, the molecular data generated in the previous step is interpreted to determine the nature and potential impact of the observed GE event. To facilitate this analysis, a comparative table is created listing the DNA sequences from both the reference genotype and the CRISPR/Cas-edited candidate genotype for each on-target and predicted off-target locus. This overview helps to clearly identify any mutations present. Once mutations are identified, an assessment is made to determine whether these are likely to be CRISPR/Cas-induced. This distinction is important, as only CRISPR/Cas-induced mutations are relevant for the RA, other mutations may occur naturally and are not subject to regulatory scrutiny. The flanking genomic regions are then used to place each allele back into its genomic context. This step is essential for understanding the biological consequences of the mutation, as it enables the evaluation of whether any known genes or regulatory elements have been disrupted. This analysis addresses the second part of EFSA's molecular characterization requirements (Addendum 1), which call for assessing whether the genetic modification affects any known coding sequences or regulatory features within the genome (EFSA Nr. 19).

Another important aspect of this interpretation phase is the assessment of gene expression (EFSA Nr. 21). However, this requirement cannot be fulfilled solely with the DNA sequence data generated in the previous step. EFSA guidelines for GMO characterization specify that data must be provided to demonstrate whether the inserted or modified gene sequence leads to the intended changes at the RNA, protein, and/or metabolite levels. This includes a description of the methods used and the associated raw datasets. This requirement can be readily translated to a GE event. Relevant expression data can be obtained through techniques such as qRT-PCR, RNA sequencing (RNA), Northern blotting (RNA), Western blotting (protein), or targeted metabolite profiling (metabolites). However, these techniques are not further elaborated here as they are not sequencing-based (except for RNA sequencing), or not specific for GE events.

5.5 Regulatory phase: Risk assessment, approval, and post-market monitoring

This final phase in the lifecycle of a GE event focuses on regulatory compliance and long-term safety assurance. It encompasses three core components: the risk assessment, the approval process, and post-market monitoring and enforcement. During the RA required (1) under the current GMO legislation, (2) if a NGT-plant is classified as NGT2 under legislative proposal, and (3) under regulatory options 1, 2, 3 and 4 (Addendum 2), the molecular characterization data generated in earlier phases is critically evaluated to determine whether the GE event

poses any safety concerns. The regulatory decision-making process itself and the post-market monitoring falls outside the scope of this report, as it is carried out by dedicated EU institutions.

6. Similarities and differences between molecular characterization approaches for candidate GE events and (transgenic) GMO events

Molecular characterization of both GE events and GMOs rely on molecular tools to identify, track, and evaluate introduced changes in the genome sequence. However, the nature of the edits and the regulatory needs dictate different strategies and technical considerations for GE versus transgenic GMO characterization.

Molecular characterization of GE events

The experimental design of CRISPR/Cas genome editing begins with the selection of target loci (for example a candidate gene), and more specifically, the design of a gRNA target sequence. The gRNA target sequence represents the core of the design, as it is the precise location where the CRISPR-induced mutation is expected to be introduced. The genome sequence position with the (perfect-match) gRNA binding site is called the “desired” or “on-target” locus. The design continues by identifying all possible loci in the genome where the gRNA can also bind with a certain maximal number of mismatches (depending on the specificity of the CRISPR/Cas enzyme; an inherent biophysical property of the Cas protein). These are called off-target loci. Ideally, off-target loci are excluded by design (the choice of the optimal gRNA that has no off-target binding sites in the genome of the reference material).

For downstream molecular characterization, it is important to unambiguously and uniquely identify all on-target and off-target loci and their respective alleles. So, in order to exclude ambiguity during interpretation of sequencing data of a GE event, it is important to already define -during the design phase- for each locus and allele, the gRNA-flanking regions that carry unique sequences that differentiate them from all other loci and alleles that share a predicted binding potential to the common gRNA. The flanking regions will facilitate placing the core sequence into genomic context and linking the mutations to a specific locus during later molecular characterization.

The molecular characterization of a GE event essentially detects all the alleles in both the reference material and the GE event, assigns them to their respective loci, pairs the respective reference and GE alleles, and tests if any of the reference alleles are mutated in the GE event, and *vice versa* if all GE alleles are accounted for by reference alleles (or may represent detection artefacts).

Taken together, targeted detection of all potentially mutated alleles (sharing a common potential gRNA binding site), is based on the sequencing of all potential gRNA binding sites and their respective flanking sequences that differentiate all alleles. The corresponding interpretation approach may be called “outside-in”; as first the flanking regions (“outside”) are used to assign sequences to their respective loci and alleles, and afterwards, the presence of a CRISPR/Cas-induced mutation in the central (gRNA binding) region of a GE allele (“in”) is detected by comparison to the corresponding reference allele sequence.

CRISPR/Cas can result in small indels (NHEJ) and single nucleotide substitutions (NHEJ, BE) at the target site. These mutations do not involve the insertion of foreign DNA, making them indistinguishable from naturally occurring mutations at molecular level without prior knowledge of the gRNA target site and CRISPR/Cas mode of action. When gene editing is performed using HDR or PE, the edits can involve the introduction of new DNA sequences. However, these sequences are typically derived from the plant’s own gene pool or closely related species

and are inserted at well-defined positions in the genome, guided by sequence homology (of the gRNA or the DRT). These expected editing outcomes should be considered during the detection and interpretation of sequence variants.

Molecular characterization of transgenic GMO events

Here, foreign DNA, e.g. a transgene, is inserted into the plant genome, often at one or more random genomic location(s). As such, molecular characterization of transgenic GMOs begins not at a known genomic target locus but instead starts with detecting the introduced DNA sequence itself. The first step is to identify the presence of this foreign DNA in the genome, followed by analysis of the adjacent flanking genomic regions to determine where the insert has been integrated (“inside-out”). Flanking sequences are essential for mapping the insertion site back to a unique genomic location in the reference genome, especially since the insertion may disrupt or affect native genes or regulatory elements. The main objectives of molecular characterization of GMOs are to determine the copy number, assess the integrity, completeness, and orientation of the inserted DNA, and evaluate potential effects on nearby genes or regulatory elements.

7. Technical recommendations for the molecular characterization of CRISPR-edited plants using High-Throughput Sequencing (HTS) technologies

During decades, several sequencing tools have been developed. First generation sequencing technologies, e.g. Sanger sequencing, are limited in resolution and not suitable for sequencing entire genomes. These limitations of first-generation sequencing methods led to the development of HTS technologies, which are capable of performing massive parallel sequencing of small DNA fragments. Several sequencing technologies and platforms are developed since the early 2000s, such as Illumina/Solexa’s Genome Analyzer, Roche/454 pyrosequencing, Polonator, ABI’s SOLiD, Helicos’ Heliscope, and ThermoFisher’s Ion Torrent [15]. Although these technologies have greatly improved in speed and cost compared to the first-generation sequencing, they all rely on PCR amplification which can cause amplification bias and generates relatively short reads (20–200 bp) [15]. To address these issues, third-generation HTS techniques were developed, such as Pacific Biosciences (PacBio) Single Molecule Real-Time (SMRT) sequencing technology and Oxford Nanopore Technology (ONT) [15]. These platforms eliminate the need for clonal amplification of the fragmented template DNAs, and generate long reads. Many applications have been developed, such as chromatin immunoprecipitation with parallel sequencing (ChIP-seq) and long-read RNA-seq. Several comprehensive reviews introduce the different HTS technologies, e.g. [15, 16, 17].

The adoption of HTS technologies to characterize GE events has been growing steadily the last years. HTS technologies have the potential to detect the nucleic acids of any organism, in some cases even without needing any *a priori* information on the genome content of the sample. With the decrease in sequencing cost, the availability of efficient DNA sequencing instruments and the improved accessibility of bioinformatic tools for analysing sequencing data, there is a rapidly increasing use of these HTS technologies. The most prominent application of HTS sequencing for the molecular characterization of GE events is the ability to detect the presence of loci and alleles that are potential targets for the CRISPR/Cas machinery, and the establishment of the corresponding DNA sequence before (Figure 2, step 1,2) and after CRISPR application (Figure 2, step 6,7). For instance, sequencing the entire genome of the reference genotype provides an overview of all candidate genes per gene family in the genome, and defines potential on-target and off-target loci that may be targeted by CRISPR/Cas gRNA recognition, and defines gRNA specificity. In addition, sequencing the genomes of a much broader set of genotypes provides insights into the genetic diversity contained within the breeders’ gene pool. Conversely, PCR amplification of one or more

specific loci followed by pooled sequencing (amplicon sequencing) can be used to efficiently detect alleles and their derived mutations at sets of predicted on-target and off-target loci.

Sequencing technologies rely on a complex succession of steps in the laboratory, but also on the bioinformatics analysis of the generated sequences. The large number of operations and the high complexity of some of them increase the risk of creating bias during analysis and can cause a lack of reliability of mutation detection and characterization. Below, we highlight various causes of false positive or false negative detection of GE alleles. Therefore, general guidelines are provided covering the process of implementation of sequencing technologies addressing the laboratory and bioinformatics steps (including personnel training and competence assessment, infrastructure, equipment and quality assurance that complies with national and international (e.g. ISO) standards). In addition, also general recommendations are given for the use of controls and result interpretation. The recommendations are inspired by those in diagnostic testing laboratories for which operational guidelines for diagnostic testing have been developed by a wide community of official reference laboratories, and approved by regulatory bodies, such as EURL, EFSA and EPPO [13, 14].

7.1 General recommendations for implementing HTS technologies for GE event characterization

Laboratory Facilities and Information Technology Infrastructure: Molecular characterization of GE events is strongly based on comparison of a candidate GE genotype with comparator reference genotypes. Since multiple materials may be handled in the same laboratory environment, any contamination between samples and/or reagents (including mix up with alternative GE genotypes and various reference genotypes of the breeders' gene pool), during extraction, library preparation (indexed primers used across multiple samples), sequencing, and bioinformatics steps (like demultiplexing) should be avoided. General guidelines on laboratory infrastructure based on a forward workflow and dedicated areas for subsequent non-compatible steps should be followed.

Personnel: Only qualified and trained personnel should process the samples and perform data analysis and interpretation. In the laboratory, personnel should be trained according to standards similarly applicable in plant diagnostics labs. For sequence data analysis, both in the design phase and in the molecular characterization of selected GE genotypes, specific IT infrastructure and bioinformatics expertise is needed. IT infrastructure includes a computational server and operating systems capable of running dedicated software, and with sufficient capacity to process large amounts of sequencing data (Gb to Tb). Trained personnel should be able to run bioinformatics pipelines correctly, including the choice of software according to the scope of the analysis, the installation, development, and updates of appropriate software and databases. In addition, relevant scientific expertise is needed to define appropriate parameter settings, for instance sequence similarity thresholds for identifying gene family members for candidate gene selection, and definition of predicted on-target and off-target loci during gRNA design, development and interpretation of mutation screening assays and differentiation between alleles and paralogous loci. In addition, bioinformatics and scientific expertise is required for the appropriate interpretation of data to avoid reporting false positive or false negative detection of GE alleles (i.e., too few or too many alleles listed as resulting from CRISPR/Cas action per GE genotype, compared to its reference genotype).

Consistent operation and traceability: While it is not a strict requirement for the molecular characterization of GE events for RA, it is recommended that laboratory and bioinformatics procedures are documented according to quality control systems and good laboratory practices. For example, sampling materials and procedures, extraction protocols and versions, library preparation reagent kits, sequencing equipment and bioinformatics software and versions, and parameter settings, etc, should be traceable.

Quality performance of outsourced services: Part of the sequencing procedure may be outsourced to NGS service providers: e.g., DNA extraction, library preparation, sequencing, and in some cases also data analysis. It is recommended to use service providers with a good analytical reputation and track record in bioinformatic analysis, and ideally a similar quality control assurance system or certification level as the GE genotype developer laboratory.

7.2 Technical recommendations for performing an HTS experiment for molecular characterization of GE events

7.2.1 Overview of the Sequencing Process

The sequencing process can be divided into eight steps. Recommendations concern the technicalities of experimental sequencing procedures. For several of these steps protocols and workflows are given in the GeneBEwise toolbox (<https://genebewise.genebecon.eu/>).

Laboratory Component:

- **Step 1. Sampling:** The sample requirements for HTS are similar to those of any other molecular diagnostic test. In the frame of providing molecular characterization of a selected GE event for RA, in most cases vegetative material (e.g., leaves) is harvested from individual plants that are homozygous or heterozygous for the mutation, and material is harvested in parallel of the comparator(s) (non-edited material from the same genetic source). Individuals carrying the GE event are expected to be genetically stable and carry the same mutation in every cell and organ of the organism. However, sometimes different sectors of the plant carry different mutations due to incomplete CRISPR/Cas action during plant regeneration and further development. If plants are generated that only carry mutations in particular organs or cell types then this aspect should be accurately described and accounted for during tissue sampling for molecular characterization, to avoid false negative detection of GE alleles (at the level of sampling).
- **Step 2. Nucleic Acid Extraction:** In case of molecular characterization of GE events, the focus lies predominantly on nuclear genomic DNA as the heritable genetic material that carries the CRISPR/Cas induced mutation. If mutations are specifically induced in organellar DNA, then that needs to be specified as part of the experimental design and included in the description of the molecular characterization. Most common plant DNA extraction protocols extract nuclear and organellar DNA, so these are fit for purpose as long as they yield DNA with a high degree of integrity and purity. For the phenotypic characterization of plants based on gene expression analysis, RNA extraction protocols are needed that yield RNA with a high degree of integrity and purity for downstream analyses such as qRT-PCR or RNA-Seq. Cross-contaminations between reference and GE genotypes should be eliminated to avoid false positive or false negative detection of GE alleles (at the level of nucleic acid extraction).
- **Step 3: Library Preparation:** the aim of the library preparation is to isolate and amplify a sufficient quantity of nucleic acids of appropriate size that are flanked with adapters required for sequencing. Adapters are short nucleotide sequences specific to the sequencing platform that enable the nucleic acid fragments to anchor the sequencer and to start the sequencing process. In addition, sample-specific indexes can be used to label individual samples before combining them and sequencing them together (multiplexed) on a sequencing run. Indexes are used to assign each nucleic acid fragment to the sample it originated from. Library preparation is done according to the sequencing approach.
 - **Shotgun sequencing:** Genomic DNA is extracted and tagged enzymatically, or fragmented to lengths compatible with the sequencing platform, and coupled to adaptors for sequencing. A wide range of commercial kits are available to create high

quality libraries. Certain regions of the genome may be less efficiently captured during library preparation or sequencing. Low sequence depth and incomplete genome coverage may lead to false negative detection of GE alleles (at the level of library preparation).

- **Amplicon sequencing**: Specific genomic regions are amplified, by PCR, and sequenced using Sanger Sequencing or HTS. Primers are designed complementary to the target sequence, allowing the amplification of the gRNA region and flanking regions (150 bp fragments for NGS, or 500-700 bp for Sanger Sequencing). Ideally, primer design is done in parallel with initial gRNA design and both should be based on knowledge of sequence diversity in the reference material at the on-target and off-target loci. gRNA can be designed to specific alleles at a particular locus, exploring the sequence diversity between target loci and using the reduction of CRISPR/Cas efficiency at increasing numbers of mismatches between the target genome sequence and gRNA sequence. Alternatively, gRNAs can be designed to conserved sequences shared by multiple alleles or paralogous sequences, thus creating multiple on-target loci per individual gRNA at which CRISPR/Cas may act simultaneously. Surrounding each gRNA binding site, two flanking primers may be designed (again taking polymorphisms that affect primer binding and PCR amplification efficiency into account) for targeted sequencing of genomic regions with predicted gRNA binding sites (including on-target and off-target loci). If primers are selected at a short distance to the expected gRNA binding site, and the repair mechanism affects a large region surrounding the double-stranded break, then amplification may fail (due to the lack of primer binding site), and the allele may not be amplified and sequenced. This may cause false negative detection of GE alleles (at the level of library preparation).
- **Pooling of samples**: (also called multiplexing) This is an option in many library preparation protocols for the sequencing of pooled samples in a single run. A unique identifier (an index, barcode, tag, molecular identifier, or MID) is a short oligonucleotide sequence flanked by an adapter that is used to tag each sample. This index is also sequenced along with the target molecules allowing each sequence to be linked to the appropriate sample after demultiplexing (see further). Indexes can be added to one end or to both ends of the nucleic acid fragment by ligation or fusion primers. Any misincorporation of indexes per sample may lead to false positive or false negative detection of GE alleles (at the level of library preparation).
- **Step 4: Sequencing**: There are several sequencing platforms that have been widely commercialized for NGS sequencing. The most used technologies are Illumina, PacBio and ONT, but alternative sequencing platforms are being developed, enter the commercial market, and are accessible through service providers (BGI-Seq, AVITI, ..). Each sequencing platform has its own specifications in terms of throughput (number of reads produced per instrument run), length of reads and base-calling quality (sequencing error profile). Error profiles inherent to the sequencing platform should be accounted for to avoid false positive detection of GE alleles (at the level of sequencing).

Bioinformatics component:

- **Step 5. Analysis of Raw Reads**: This bioinformatic step consists of several operations, including quality control of the generated sequences (depending on the sequencing technology), elimination of low-quality sequences, and removal of the adaptor, index, and primer sequences. In the case of pooled samples, demultiplexing is needed and enables the correct assignment of the generated sequences to each sample. Optionally, some additional analysis can be performed to reduce the amount of data and to improve the quality of the analysis, e.g., merging forward and reverse reads (based on overlapping regions), or removing duplicated (identical) reads.

- **Step 6. Identification of alleles per target region:** This bioinformatic step (= allele identification and variant detection) aims to associate sequences with specific genomic locations and differentiates between reads derived from closely related sequences at independent genomic loci on the one hand (for instance paralogs), and the various alleles per locus on the other hand. Allele identification at on-target and off-target loci relies on comparison with an existing annotated reference genome sequence, for instance, through read mapping. Alternative to read mapping, *de novo* assembly may be performed on the raw reads, after which BLAST analysis may identify contigs that contain 'foreign' DNA sequences (such as delivery vectors used during transfection) that can potentially be introduced into the genome during the process of creating DSBs and repair. Such inserts should be confirmed by independent assembly-free methods, like targeted amplification of the locus containing the insert for example with long-range PCR followed by long read sequencing. The assignment of alleles per target locus should be based on sequence identity of the regions flanking the potential target edit site, because after the CRISPR/Cas action the sequence at the gRNA binding site are expected to be changed (thus leading to mismatches with the original genomic locus), while the unchanged flanking regions are still derived from the original genomic locus. These regions should be defined long enough to contain sufficient sequence diversity to unambiguously differentiate between reads from paralogous loci in the reference genome. These parameters should be validated prior to CRISPR/Cas editing to avoid ambiguous interpretation of data from the GE genotype. After mapping of reads derived from the reference material and of the candidate GE genotype, variant calling algorithms dedicated to SNP calling or InDel calling are applied to detect sequence variants per locus. In addition, several algorithms have been developed that specifically analyse CRISPR/Cas induced mutations in Sanger Sequencing data or NGS sequencing data. If mutated alleles are changed in a way the prohibits read mapping to its original location (flanking regions not defined long enough), then this allele is not accounted for in the list of existing alleles per locus. This may cause false negative detection of a GE allele (at the level of detection).
- **Step 7. Analysis of Controls:** If during the molecular characterization of the GE genome PCR artefacts or sequencing errors create alternative reads that are mapped to their original genomic locus, these may cause false positive detection of GE alleles, as they are not accounted for by a reference counterpart. PCR replicates may be used as confirmation controls for potential false positive detection of GE alleles. Along the same lines, both positive and negative controls may be implemented throughout the sequencing and analysis process.
- **Step 8. Target Confirmation, Interpretation and Reporting:** After detecting the various alleles at each of the predicted on-target and off-target loci, they can be listed in a table that links the alleles detected in the (non-edited) reference material, to the alleles in the candidate GE genotype. In principle, all reference alleles that are also detected in the GE event, are considered non-edited. All reference alleles that are not detected in the candidate GE genotype are considered potentially edited but need to be confirmed by a detected allele unique to the GE event that is identical at the flanking regions and different around the predicted gRNA binding site (or other predicted editing outcome). Thus, allele variants that are detected in a GE genotype but not detected in the reference genotype and that cannot be explained by the expected outcomes of CRISPR/Cas action (depending on predictability of the CRISPR/Cas - gRNA binding site specificity and of the repair mechanism), may cause false positive detection of GE alleles. If for some reason (e.g., GE genotype genomic DNA contamination in the reference genomic DNA extract) a true GE mutated allele is also detected in the reference genomic DNA, then the above reasoning excludes it from being listed as a mutated allele, since it is accounted for the same allele detected in the reference. This may cause false negative detection of a GE allele (at the level of interpretation).

7.2.2 Recommendations for obtaining high-quality molecular data

Below we present a table to list the risks leading to the production of poor-quality molecular data per step of the sequencing process, the causes and consequences, and recommendations for mitigation of those risks as guidelines for performing successful molecular characterization of GE genotypes based on HTS. The table is adapted from [13, 14].

Table 1: Table summarizing risks leading to the production of poor-quality data in different steps of the sequencing process and guidelines to mitigate the different risks. The table is adapted from [13, 14]. (FP= False Positive; FN= False Negative)

HTS step	Risk	Cause	Consequence	Mitigation
Sampling and sample handling	Cross-contamination between samples	Inappropriate sampling procedure.	FP FN	Protocol to describe measures to minimize cross contamination. Use appropriate threshold values to discard contamination sequences.
Nucleic acid extraction	Inappropriate integrity and purity of nucleic acids	Inhibitors in the matrix, reagent lot or inappropriate handling/storage conditions of reagents and/or samples affect nucleic acid extraction.	FN	Protocol describing the control and integrity of nucleic acids with appropriate thresholds.
	Low quantity of nucleic acids	Low quantity of biological input material or inappropriate nucleic acid extraction procedure.	FN	Protocol describing the minimal quantity of biological material required and the control of the quantity of nucleic acids with appropriate thresholds.
	Cross-contamination between samples	See cross contamination between samples during sampling		
Library preparation for shotgun sequencing	Content bias (fragment size and concentration of nucleic acids) related to protocol used	Library protocol (dis)favoring some targets, PCR amplification favoring smaller fragment sizes and GC content, complex sequence structures not included in library.	FN	Proper definition of the scope of the HTS analyses (gene family identification, gRNA specificity check, genetic diversity screen, mutant allele detection, ..), and selection of the most appropriate protocol with appropriate thresholds.
PCR for amplicon sequencing and some shotgun sequencing	Amplification error	Fidelity of the polymerase can create errors in the generated strand resulting in false mutation that can bias the sequence annotation.	FP	Use high fidelity polymerase. Check target sequences from positive controls or PCR replicates.
	Bias during amplification	Modification of proportion of detected alleles. Creation of a large proportion of duplicated reads.	FN Bias in allele estimation	Appropriate primer selection. Set a maximum number of PCR cycles. Use of positive controls with targets at known concentration. Monitor the read duplication rate.

	Missing low abundance target due to low input quantity of nucleic acids	The quantity of nucleic acids for PCR is usually very small and rare targets might be missed.	FN	Rising the quantity of nucleic acids in PCR reaction while avoiding bias. Use of replicates of PCR reactions.
	Cross-contamination between samples	See cross contamination between samples during sampling		
Sample indexing and pooling	Unequal representation of samples in the pool with samples sequenced at low read depth	Unreliable quantification of prepared nucleic acids between samples of favored sequencing from some sample(s) in pools.	FN	Check quantity of extracted nucleic acids using appropriate protocol. Monitor sequencing depth per sample after demultiplexing and set a minimal sequence depth.
	Index-hopping (a small proportion of sequences is tagged with the wrong index (and assigned to wrong sample during demultiplexing))	Presence of free index in the reaction getting tagged randomly to sample. Tag-jumps where indexed primer starts extension, but amplicon is not complete. Incomplete fragment then acts as primer in next PCR cycle binding on the temple of another locus or sample, and creating a chimeric amplicon with index tag switch.	FN FP	Use highly distinct and unique index between two sequencing runs. Dual labelling index is preferred for Illumina sequencing. Monitor index switching and cross-contamination between library preparation and sequencing runs. Check the number or % of unexpected sequences in controls.
	Unequal size of the prepared nucleic acids between samples	The size of the prepared nucleic acids may influence the sequencing yield of the sample or the amplicon.	FN	Define acceptable range in sequence length in prepared libraries. Pool PCR products of similar length or shear samples at an appropriate size.
Sequencing	Not enough sequencing reads	Presence of inhibitor in one of the samples. Poor sequencing reagents. Under- or overloading the sequencing device with DNA.	FN	Set minimal sequencing depth per sample.
	Low quality of nucleotide bases	Sequencing reagents, accuracy of signal measurement, background signal. Low quality and incorrect sequences will be generated and can be eliminated during reads analysis or introduce errors during bioinformatic analyses.	FN FP	Set minimal sequencing depth per sample. Monitor the number of reads eliminated or retained per sample after reads analyses.
	Sequencing errors	Type of sequencing platform and sequencing method	FN FP	Use of appropriate controls to evaluate the sequencing fidelity (positive controls with

		(including sequencing reagents).		known allele constitution, PhiX control with Illumina technology).
	Inter-run contamination	Traces of libraries from a previous run are sequenced.	FP	Proper washing of the sequencing machine and alternate the indices between runs. Detecting indices used during the previous run (when alternating indices between runs)
Data storage	Data storage capacity, corrupted data, loss of data.	IT computational system not adapted for handling and storing HTS data	Corrupted and or loss of data	Procedure detailing the required storage capacity including backup, safe storage of data, and retention period.
First step of the bioinformatics analyses	GC bias	Target sequences with high GC content are currently not well sequenced. The sequence coverage of these regions can be absent or very low compared to other targets.	FN	Determine the extent of GC bias for HTS testing with comparable regions with similar GC content. Follow GC content statistics of the sequencing.
	Inappropriate demultiplexing	Inappropriate demultiplexing software and parameters might fail to assign a small portion of the sequences to the correct samples. Inappropriate combination of sequencing indices detected within a run.	FN FP	Verify the compatibility of demultiplexing parameters and software with the used indexes. Use highly distinct and unique index between two sequencing runs.
Second step of the bioinformatics analyses	Low quality of reads assembly	the use of too stringent parameters during the assembly of reads can hamper read assembly, (i.e. split alleles across independent contigs), while higher tolerance to mismatches can create assembly artefacts (e.g. compression of paralogs into a single consensus reference contig).	FN FP	Set appropriate thresholds for the parameters of reads assembly quality. Monitor the parameters of reads assembly quality in each run using appropriate controls.
	Low read mapping quality	The reference genome sequence (partial or complete, haploid representation or haplotype-resolved T2T) used and its completeness and curation level, and the parameters of read mapping can create bias: incorrect mapping of reads on a reference	FN FP	Set appropriate thresholds for the parameters of read mapping quality, such as percentage of identity with reference sequence, quality of assembled genomes. Monitor the parameters of mapping quality in each run using appropriate controls. Check the suitability of the reference sequence and/or sequence database.

		of another individual (or even of an other species), or absence of mapping due to incompleteness of the genome, or strong sequence diversity (in wild-type reference reads or after mutagenesis).		
	Non-uniform coverage of the genome	Variation of read depth or absence of coverage can be due to low abundance of the target, the use of a distant reference genome sequence, the difficulty of sequencing a certain part of the genome.	FN	Set the minimum criteria for the level of coverage across the sequenced regions (which may be partial or full genome). Monitor the uniformity of coverage in each run using appropriate controls.
	Wrong interpretation of functional and structural consequences of mutant alleles	Reference genome completeness and accuracy are essential for proper annotation of candidate genes, on-target and off-target loci, pseudogenes, etc. Software methodology, and threshold parameters could also influence the results and interpretation. The particular case is outside the knowledge/knowhow of the bioinformatician performing target selection and gRNA/primer design.	FN FP	Set appropriate thresholds to ensure the reliable identification of targets according to locus and allele demarcation criteria. Monitor the assignment of alleles to loci, using appropriate criteria. Check the suitability of the reference sequence and/or reference sequence database. Personnel competent in the bioinformatic analyses and the relevant genome science discipline (e.g., gene annotation and sequence variation).
	Variant not identified or false variant identified	The identification of variants can be done according to different methodologies, each depending on several parameters. It also depends on the quality control of the reads (e.g. SNPs can originate from low quality reads or sequencing errors).	FN FP	Set appropriate threshold parameters, minimal SNP frequency, coverage, base calling quality, strand bias, insertion/deletion size, to ensure the reliable identification of mutant alleles. Controlled artificial datasets could be used to validate the bioinformatics procedure. Sequencing replicates of a single sample.
Third step of the bioinformatics analyses	Targets of control samples not retrieved	One or several thresholds of parameters from the previous steps have not been set accurately.	FN FP	Set appropriate threshold parameters to ensure the reliable identification of controls. Controlled artificial datasets could be used to validate the bioinformatics procedure.

8. Case Studies

8.1. Microalgae case study

Microalgae are known for their rapid growth and metabolic versatility, hence presenting a sustainable alternative to traditional agriculture for the production of high-value compounds. Furthermore, CRISPR/Cas can be useful to enhance the production of these high-value compounds in microalgae. In GeneBEcon, the aim was to develop a CRISPR/Cas mutant microalgae strain with an increased production of carotenoids, more specifically zeaxanthin and violaxanthin, by targeting key enzymes in the carotenoid biosynthetic pathway in the microalgae species *Nannochloropsis*.

Pre-characterization phase: CRISPR design and generation of CRISPR-edited genotype

The microalga *Nannochloropsis oceanica* (a haploid organism with a genome of approximately 30 Mb) was used. An increase in the carotenoids was attempted by relying on CRISPR/Cas9 DSBs and imperfect NHEJ repair mechanism, which introduces small insertions or deletions at the target site, potentially resulting in a frameshift in the ORF leading to gene disruption. By disrupting specific genes in the carotenoid biosynthesis pathway, the levels of industrially relevant carotenoids, specifically zeaxanthin and violaxanthin, can be increased.

In total, 8 gRNAs were designed using a reference genome of the same *Nannochloropsis* strain used in the lab, which is publicly available at NCBI (GCA_001870945.1), to target the following genes: *zeaxanthin epoxidase 1 (ZEP1)*, *zeaxanthin epoxidase 2 (ZEP2)*, *violaxanthin de-epoxidase (VDE)*, and *violaxanthin de-epoxidase-like (VDL)*. Sanger sequencing was done to check for any genetic variation in the target genes between the publicly available reference genome and the genome of the lab strain to ensure that designed gRNAs would be able to bind. For each target gene and its corresponding gRNA target sequence (core sequence), sequences with high similarity were identified using CRISPOR (allowing up to four mismatches) [18], and all compiled into a list (Figure 7).

approximately three days and included colony PCR (cPCR) with the designed primers, PCR product purification, Sanger sequencing, and subsequent data analysis. Data analysis was performed using both the bioinformatics software Geneious Prime and ICE (<https://www.synthego.com/products/bioinformatics/analysis>).

In Geneious (<https://www.geneious.com/>), the quality of each Sanger sequencing electropherogram was evaluated for sharp, non-overlapping peaks with minimal background noise. Poor-quality regions, especially at the beginning or end of the sequence, were trimmed. The trimmed reads were aligned to the reference sequence, and disruptions around the expected CRISPR site were examined, indicating the presence of mutations.

In total, two mutants with mutations in the *VDL* gene, responsible for the conversion of violaxanthin into neoxanthin, were obtained (Figure 8). Sequence alignment revealed a one-nucleotide insertion (K1; T inserted) and a two-nucleotide insertion (K5; TT inserted), compared to the reference sequence (WT).

Figure 8: Alignment of the Sanger sequencing results of two mutants (K1 and K5) to the WT in Geneious Prime. The alignment shows an insertion of one thymine nucleotide in K1 and an insertion of two thymine nucleotides in K5. The gRNA (*VDL_gRNA1*) is indicated in blue and the PAM sequence in green.

The analysis was initially performed in Geneious (<https://www.geneious.com/>), but similar analyses can be automated using tools like ICE (<https://www.synthego.com/products/bioinformatics/analysis>) or TIDE. (<https://tide.nki.nl/>). The electropherogram from K1 was also analysed in ICE (Figure 9), which does not require prior trimming of sequences and provides additional information such as KO scores, indel distribution, etc.

Figure 9: The ICE analysis results of the K1 mutant compared to the WT.

Molecular characterization phase: Detailed sequence analysis of selected candidate GE genotypes at on-target and off-target loci

After screening, only two CFUs showed a mutation, and both were selected for further molecular characterization both on the intended on-target loci and potential off-target loci, defined as sequences with high similarity to the gRNA target sequence. However, for the *VDL* gene using gRNA1, no potential off-target loci were identified, that is, no sequences with up to four mismatches to the *VDL* gRNA1 target sequence were found (Figure 7). Sequencing data are therefore only generated for the on-target allele in the wild type and in the mutants (Figure

8, 9). Since no potential off-target alleles were identified, the molecular characterization was concluded at this point. This highlights the importance of careful gRNA design to minimize potential predictable off-target sequences, thereby significantly reducing the workload during molecular characterization.

Interpretation phase: comparative list of alleles and estimation of effect on gene function

The mutation in both K1 and K5 occurred 3 bp upstream of the PAM sequence, as expected for CRISPR/Cas9-induced double-stranded breaks. The mutation type, a short insertion of one (K1) or two (K5) nucleotides, is a common outcome of the (imperfect) NHEJ repair pathway. Therefore, it can be concluded that the observed mutation was caused by CRISPR/Cas9 activity. Given that the number of inserted nucleotides is not a multiple of three, a frameshift mutation is expected in both cases. To confirm this and assess the functional consequence, the mutant alleles were placed back into their genomic context and translated into protein sequences. The outcome is shown in Figure 10, where both mutations result in a premature stop codon.

Figure 10: Translated protein sequence resulting from the replacement of the WT allele with the mutant alleles (K1 and K5). The coding sequence is highlighted in yellow, the mutations are indicated with a blue stripe, and the resulting premature stop codons are marked with an asterisk and a grey arrow.

In the case of the one-nucleotide insertion (K1), the resulting transcript encodes only 30% of the original protein. The two-nucleotide insertion (K5) leads to a transcript encoding just 9% of the full-length protein. Both mutations are therefore likely to result in the translation of a non-functional protein. A gene expression analysis was not performed, as this cannot be achieved using the DNA sequence data described above and would require additional experiments.

8.2. Potato case study

A combination of different CRISPR/Cas-based technologies were used on *Solanum tuberosum* (potato) to improve resistance to Potato Virus Y (PVY) and enhance the potato starch quality. PVY is an insect-transmitted virus that can cause a high yield loss. Improved starch quality is important for the starch industry, as it could reduce or eliminate the need for the chemical and physical processing currently required for most applications of potato starch. The example presented here from the potato case study focuses on gene editing to improve the starch quality. To achieve this, several *starch synthase* (SS) genes were targeted using a two-step gene-editing approach (Figure 11). In the first step, targeted mutagenesis via NHEJ was performed on genes encoding three *starch synthase* genes, *GBSS*, *SS2* and *SS3*. In the second step, HDR was applied on top of the *starch synthase* mutations to insert a potato tuber-specific regulatory element, i.e., a strong *GBSS* promoter sequence, upstream of a fourth soluble *starch synthase* gene *SS1*. Enhancing the tissue-specific expression of *SS1* in tubers is expected to increase starch content while maintaining the improved quality resulting from the earlier edits. In this case study we describe the molecular characterization of the *GBSS* promoter insertion. The reference lab material in this case is potato cultivar 'Kuras' in which NHEJ mutations are already present (and characterized) in *GBSS*, *SS2* and *SS3* genes.

Figure 11: Overview of the two-step approach followed to improve the starch quality in potato by applying CRISPR/Cas tools. In a first step, NHEJ is attempted to knockout the *GBSS*, *SS2* and *SS3* genes. Knocking out the *GBSS* gene will lead to inactivation of the amylose molecules in the starch. Combined with the chain length changes of amylopectin by knocking out the *SS* genes, this will lead to better quality starch. In a second step, a strong *GBSS* promoter element will be inserted upstream of the *SS1* gene by HDR, also leading to chain length changes in amylopectin. This last step will be described in more detail below in the text.

Pre-characterization phase: CRISPR design and generation of CRISPR-edited genotype

HDR was used to introduce the *GBSS* promoter sequence upstream of the *SS1* gene in the (modified) potato cultivar 'Kuras' (a tetraploid organism with a genome of approximately 3.1 Gb, and with characterized NHEJ mutations in *GBSS*, *SS2* and *SS3* genes). To enable this, a gRNA (gRNA_T17) was designed using the Cas-designer tool (<https://www.genscript.com/tools/gRNA-design-tool/>). Based on the gRNA target sequence (core sequence), sequences with high similarity (allowing up to four mismatches) were identified in the haploid DH v6.1 reference genome assembly in NCBI and compiled into a list (Figure 13). For donor repair template (DRT; Figure 12) preparation, a synthetic plasmid was used (pDRT_SS1_GBSSp; Thermo Fisher Scientific) containing the *GBSS* promoter sequence flanked by sequences homologous to the *SS1* locus. The plasmid served as template in PCR reactions to produce the DRT. To introduce the promoter sequence into protoplasts, PEG-mediated transfection was used.

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CTGAGTATCTGTCCACCTCTTTCTAGGTACTTGTGTTCTTCATCAGATCCTATAAAGCTTTAACGAGATAGAAAATTATGTTA
CTCCGTTTTGTTTCATTACTTAACAAATGCAACAGTATCTTGACCAAATCCTTCTCTCTTTTCAAACCTTTTCTATTTGGCTGT
TGACAGAGTAATCAGGATACAAACCACAAGTATTTAATTGACTCATCCACCAGATAATTATGATTTATGAATCCTCGAAAAGCC
TATCCATTAAGTTCTCATCTATGGATATACTTGACAGTTTCTTCTATTTGGGTATTTTTTTTTTCCGCAAGTGGAACGGAG
ACATGTTATGTTGTATACGGGAAGCTCGTTAAAAAATAACAATAGGAAGAAAATGTAACAAACATTGAATGTTGTTTTTA
ACCATCCTTCTTTTAGCAGTGTATCAATTTGTAATAGAACCATGCATCTCAATCTTAATACTAAAAAATGCAACAAAATTC
TAGTGGAGGGACCAGTACCAGTACATTAGATATTATTTTTTATTACTATAATAATATTTTAATTAACACGAGACATAGGAATG
TCAAGTGGTAGCGGTAGGAGGGAGTTGGTTAGTTTTTTAGATACTAGGAGACAGAACCAGGAGGGGCCCATTTGCAAGGCCCAA
GTTGAAGTCCAGCCGTGAATCAACAAAGAGAGGGCCATAAATACTGTGCGATGAGCATTTCCTATAATACAGTGTCCACAGTT
GCCTTCCGCTAAGGGATAGCCACCCGCTATTCTCTTGACACGTGTCAGTAAACCTGCTACAAATAAGGCAGGCACCTCCTCA
TTCTCACACTCACTCACTCACACAGCTCAACAAGTGGTAACTTTTACTCATCTCTCCAATTATTTCTGATTTTCATGCACTAG
TACTGTAGTAGTAGAATATCAATATAGAATGAGTGTTC

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Figure 12: DRT used for the insertion of the *GBSS* promoter via HDR. The homology arms are highlighted in green and flank the *GBSS* promoter sequence.

Figure 13: The target locus for the insertion of the GBBS promoter with corresponding non-target loci. The target locus is indicated as 'TL' and the analyzed non-target loci are indicated with 'OFF'. The core is highlighted in purple, and within each core, the PAM sequence is underlined.

Screening phase: Molecular analysis of regenerants and selection of candidate GE event

In total, 330 individual regenerants were produced. Of these, 179 were screened by PCR to assess the presence or absence of the DRT. PCR primers were designed to amplify the region flanking the Cas9 cut site, and differences in amplicon size were analyzed using gel electrophoresis. If the DRT was successfully introduced, a larger amplicon was obtained. The insertion upstream of the SS1 gene was confirmed in 27 regenerated GE events. Five of the identified mutant regenerants were selected, where one GE event, M11070, was used for detailed molecular characterization.

Molecular characterization phase: Detailed sequence analysis of selected candidate GE event at on-target and off-target loci

For M11070, ONT sequencing was used to obtain more detailed nucleotide-level information at the on-target locus. The obtained DNA sequence, shown in Figure 14, confirms that the DRT was successfully inserted upstream of the *SS1* gene.

Figure 14: DNA sequence of mutant M11070 with the inserted *GBBS* promoter upstream of the *SS1* gene. The used gRNA is highlighted in blue, the PAM sequence in green. The DRT was successfully introduced 3 bp upstream of the PAM sequence.

Additionally, two predicted off-target loci (OFF1 and OFF2, Figure 13) were amplified by PCR and submitted for Sanger sequencing analysis at Eurofins Genomics (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Sanger sequencing results of two predicted off-target sites of both the reference material and the mutant analyzed in CLC Genomics Workbench.

Sanger sequencing results were analyzed using CLC Genomics Workbench. The mutant DNA sequence is identical to the wild-type (WT) DNA sequence at the predicted off-target site. For OFF1, some differences between the WT and mutant sequences were observed in the flanking region; however, these are likely due to low sequencing quality, as multiple peaks appear in the electropherogram. Across all analyzed predicted off-target sites, no off-target mutations were detected. To fulfill the required molecular characterization, all predicted off-target loci (listed in Figure 12) should be sequenced, either by Sanger sequencing (as shown to be effective above) or HTS. However, due to time constraints, this has not yet been done for the potato case study in GeneBEcon.

Interpretation phase: comparative list of alleles and estimation of effect on gene function

The insertion of the DRT (the *GBSS* promoter) occurred 3 bp upstream of the PAM sequence, as expected for CRISPR/Cas9-induced double-stranded breaks. The mutation type, i.e., the insertion of the DRT, is the expected outcome of the HDR repair pathway. Therefore, it can be concluded that the observed mutation was caused by CRISPR/Cas9 activity.

9. Conclusion

The development and application of gene editing technologies, particularly CRISPR/Cas, hold immense promise for advancing a sustainable and low-impact agriculture and bioeconomy in Europe. However, gene editing is only as powerful as the evidence supporting it. Molecular characterization is essential for safe and acceptable innovation and should be accompanied by robust scientific scrutiny, transparent practices, and an adaptive regulatory framework. This report contributes directly to that goal by offering a detailed, practical, and science-based roadmap for the molecular characterization of gene-edited (GE) plants.

Across the full gene editing life cycle, from experimental design and gRNA selection to sequencing, allele analysis, and RA, clear and actionable guidelines are outlined and supported by practical tools (e.g., the GeneBEwise toolbox). It is highlighted that tailored molecular strategies are needed for GE versus transgenic (GMO) events. In addition, case studies in potato and microalgae showcase the real-world applicability of the methods described.

At the heart of the molecular characterization process is the use of high-throughput sequencing (HTS) technologies, which enable the detection and interpretation of both on-target and (predicted) off-target genomic changes. The HTS technologies, when implemented under strict quality control and supported by validated bioinformatics pipelines, provide the resolution, reliability, and reproducibility needed for regulatory compliance and public confidence. The technical recommendations, including a comprehensive risk matrix for HTS workflows, offer essential support to developers and regulatory bodies in managing the complexity and nuance of genome editing.

In addition, the document demonstrates how regulatory expectations differ depending on the editing strategy (e.g., NHEJ vs. HDR), the presence or absence of foreign DNA, and the classification of GE events as NGT1 or NGT2 under the proposed EU framework. This flexibility demands case-by-case scientific evaluation, but it also requires clear regulatory alignment and consistency. One-size-fits-all regulation no longer suffices. Tailored, risk-proportionate approaches are needed for NGTs.

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11. Addenda

ADDENDUM 1 – Molecular characterization under EFSA

Nr.	EFSA requirement	Translation to NGT
Information on recipient and parental plants		
1	Complete name (family, genus, species, subspecies, cultivar/breeding line/strain, common name) of recipient and parental plants	Exact genotype and genetic background
2	Geographical distribution and cultivation of the plant	Geographical background of the genotype
3	Info on recipient and parental plants relevant for their safety (known toxicity, allergenicity, constituents)	Breeding history of the genotype
4	Data on present and past use of recipient organism (history of safe use): how is the plant cultivated, transported, and stored? Is special processing needed before eating it? What is the normal role of the plant in a normal diet? Which part is for consumption? Etc.	
Methods used for genetic transformation		
5	Method of genetic transformation (plus bibliographic references)	What NGT application is done (NHEJ, HDR, PE, BE)?; What Cas enzyme is used?; What transfection method is used (Biolistics, PEG-mediated, electroporation, Agrobacterium-mediated)?; Is a repair template used?; What is the origin/sequence of the template?
6	Species/strain of Agrobacterium/rhizobacterium that is used for transformation	Only when Agrobacterium-mediated transformation is used: information on the Agrobacterium strain (what strain, sequence, elements, etc.)
7	Helper plasmids that are used for transformation	If plasmid DNA is used: information on the plasmid use (E. coli) (what strain, sequence, elements, etc.)
8	Carrier DNA that is used during transformation	Details on the RNP, if RNPs are used (protocol of assembly, Cas-enzyme details, etc.)
Information on nucleic acids intended to be inserted		
9	Complete sequence, including information on deliberate alterations to	Information on the induced modification, including

	the corresponding sequence in the donor	information on gene/gene family that has been targeted (what target gene and what is the function), sequence data on target (e.g. 100 bp upstream and 100 bp downstream or larger if large deletion or complex rearrangement); sequence of the gRNA; also in case of HDR, the sequence and origin of the repair template.
10	History of safe use of the gene products arisen from the regions intended for insertion	Only translatable for cisgenesis (NGT2): source, size and intended function of sequence that is inserted; discussion whether the nature of the inserted sequence may trigger any safety issue; are endogenous genes or regulatory sequences been interrupted by integration?
11	Data on relationship of the gene products with known toxins, anti-nutrients, and allergens	Only translatable for cisgenesis (NGT2): data on the possible relationship of the gene product with known toxins, anti-nutrients, and allergens
Information on the vector(s) used including nucleotide sequences intended for insertion		
12	Physical map of the functional elements and other plasmid/vector components + information needed for the interpretation of the molecular analysis (restriction sites, primer positions, probes localisation, etc.) also the region intended for insertion should be clearly indicated.	(see also EFSA nr.7): information on the plasmid vector used: what strain, plasmid/vector elements, sequence, vector map with annotations of the different elements, primers, restriction sites, probes, etc.
13	Table identifying each component of the plasmid/vector, its size, its origin, its intended function	Information on the total assembly of the plasmid vector that is used: what expression vectors were used (origin, sequence), what elements are used from which expression vector; what cloning system was used; what overhangs, etc.
Description of traits and characteristics which have been introduced or modified		
14	General description of the introduced trait(s) and its mode of action	(See also EFSA nr. 9) Information on the target gene, general description on its function in the pathway or molecular network

15	General description of resulting changes in the phenotype and metabolism of the plant and of its intended use.	General description of the resulting modification on the phenotype or metabolism of the organism. Are regulatory sequences targeted? What new trait is the mutated organism presenting compared to the existing organism?
Information on the sequences inserted/deleted or altered		
16	Size and copy number of all detectable inserts (complete and partial). Typically, by southern analysis complete coverage of the inserted sequence, including any part of the plasmid/vector, remaining carrier, and foreign nucleic acid. Span the entire transgenic locus/loci and the flanking sequences	Only relevant when performing HDR or PE
17	Organisation and sequence of the inserted genetic material at each insertion site	Only relevant when performing HDR or PE
18	Sub-cellular location of the inserts (nucleus, plastid, mitochondrial) and method for determination of this	Only relevant when performing HDR or PE
19	Sequence information for both 5' and 3' flanking regions at each insertion site (aim is to identify interruptions of known genes); use of up-to-date databases and perform both intra-species and inter-species similarity searches; if stacked events, safety of potential interactions between modifications at each insertion site should be assessed.	
20	ORF present within the insert and spanning junction sites should be analysed between stop codons, not limiting their lengths	Only relevant when performing HDR or PE
Information on the expression of the inserted sequence		
21	Demonstrate whether the inserted/modified sequence results in intended changes at the protein, RNA, and metabolite level. Protein expression data; analysis of specific RNA(s) or metabolite(s); data should be derived from plants grown under conditions representative of typical cultivation practices with a minimum of 3	

	<p>growing sites or from one site over 3 seasons.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Methods used and raw datasets should be given If insert encodes new protein(s), the range and mean values for the level of the newly produced protein(s) should be provided. Selection of a good comparator! A similar food or feed produced without the help of genetic modification and for which there is a well-established history of safe use; a “conventional counterpart”; a non-GM isogenic variety; a genotype with a genetic background as close as possible to the GM plant. See comparative characterization 	
<p><i>Information on the genetic stability of the inserted sequence (and phenotypic stability) of the GM plant</i></p>		
22	<p>Demonstration of the genetic stability of the transgenic locus/loci (and the phenotypic stability) and inheritance pattern(s) of the introduced trait(s). for stacked events, the integrity of the events should be demonstrated. >> data from 5 generations or vegetative cycles</p>	<p>Only relevant when HDR or PE?</p>

ADDENDUM 2 – Regulatory options defined by GeneBEcon for the future of genome editing regulation

Reference: [5, 12]

Option 1: the legal status quo remains unchanged, and no differentiation is made between GMOs and NGT plants. Here, the full data is required as defined in the current GMO law (inter alia Dir. 2001/18/EC and Reg. (EC) No. 1829/2003 for food and feed) for authorisation of the new NGT plant.

Option 1 is the baseline defined by the current GMO legislation.

Option 2: the foundations of the legal framework remain unchanged. However, the data requirements for RA follow the principle laid out for Category 2 NGT plants as proposed by EC on July 5, 2023 (which originally excludes microalgae).

Option 3: regulating plants according to whether they are (1) conventional-like, (2) non-conventional-like or (3) non-conventional-like with hypothesis for harm, after initial verification by a CA. Cfr. EU proposal

Option 4: a product-based approach addressing risks associated with novel traits. Every novel trait would be assessed for putative risks, and, if applicable, a focused risk assessment is done.

Option 5: the NGT plant must be free of foreign DNA (understood as DNA out of the breeders' gene pool) to be exempted from a specific regulation. The applicant shall prove the absence of foreign DNA during the verification process.

Option 6: “no data, no market” approach like REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals). The applicant shall provide a portfolio with the necessary data. For all options, diverse needs are determined in terms of risk assessment, verification data, and authorization (Figure 1; table 1).

Figure 1 NGT plants and GeneBEcon regulatory options. Requirements for Verification Data (VD), Risk Assessment (RA), and final Authorization by a Competent Authority for NGT plants (green full line) vary between the different Options. Conventional (grey dotted line) or transgenic plants (red dotted line) are shown when applicable under the Option. All plants that are considered not safe would be rejected under every option.

Table 1: Data requirements for general principles and information In Part 1.1 Information required for verification process are specified. "Yes" and "No" indicates that this information point is required under the specific Option. Cost calculations are found in Annex 2 (Excel file)

1.1.	<u>General principles and information on...</u>	Option 2	Option 3	Option 4	Option 5	Option 6	
1.1.1	the characteristics of the NGT plant, in particular the trait(s) introduced, (the) function of the modified or inserted genome sequence(s) and the function of any gene disrupted by the insertion of a cisgene or parts thereof*	Yes	Yes				
1.1.2	prior experience with the consumption of similar plants or their products (when food and feed)*		Yes, if not conventional-like	Yes	Yes, if foreign DNA	Yes	
1.1.3	prior experience with the cultivation of the same plant species or plant species exhibiting similar traits or in which similar genome sequences have been modified, inserted or disrupted*						
1.1.4	the scale and conditions of the release*			No			
1.1.5	the intended conditions of use of the NGT plant*		Yes				
1.1.6	information on used NGT methods (transformation/infection, segregation of transgene, repair template, used plasmids, relevant information needed for the interpretation of the molecular analyses)		Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes if applicant decides
1.1.7	identification of potential off-target sites (potentially affected locus (PAL))		No		No		
1.1.8	testing for unintended integration of foreign DNA					Yes	
1.1.9	for cis- and intragenesis: Source of nucleic acid(s) used for transformation, size and intended function of each constituent fragment of the region intended for insertion		Yes			Yes	
1.1.10	conclusions of the molecular characterization		Yes				

* Data requirements of category 2 NGT plants defined by the proposal on the European Commission on plants obtained by certain NGTs and their food and feed

ADDENDUM 3 – Annex I of the EU proposal

Reference: [6]

ANNEX I**Criteria of equivalence of NGT plants to conventional plants**

A NGT plant is considered equivalent to conventional plants when it differs from the recipient/parental plant by no more than 20 genetic modifications of the types referred to in points 1 to 5, in any DNA sequence sharing sequence similarity with the targeted site that can be predicted by bioinformatic tools.

- (1) substitution or insertion of no more than 20 nucleotides;
- (2) deletion of any number of nucleotides;
- (3) on the condition that the genetic modification does not interrupt an endogenous gene:
 - (a) targeted insertion of a contiguous DNA sequence existing in the breeder's gene pool;
 - (b) targeted substitution of an endogenous DNA sequence with a contiguous DNA sequence existing in the breeder's gene pool;
- (4) targeted inversion of a sequence of any number of nucleotides;
- (5) any other targeted modification of any size, on the condition that the resulting DNA sequences already occur (possibly with modifications as accepted under points (1) and/or (2)) in a species from the breeders' gene pool.

12. RRI Questionnaire

Question	Answer
1. How the RRI concept has been considered in the completed work?	N/A
2. Have stakeholders been consulted during the work?	Not directly. However, for writing this deliverable report documents from EFSA, EPPO, EURLs are consulted. These entities can also be considered as stakeholders from the project.
a. How?	EFSA and EPPO Publications were used.
b. What inputs have been obtained during the interaction with the stakeholders?	N/A
c. Have these inputs changed the considerations of the work?	N/A
3. In involving stakeholders, did you have to explain the science behind the work? Please explain how you did this.	N/A
4. Explain the Ethical procedures you are following in the course of the completed work.	Principles and guidelines that ensure the responsible and moral conduct of scientific research are followed by the different partners. These include but are not limited to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - partners must handle and dispose of biological materials according to EU directives and laws, - partners must have an informed consent from participants before involving them in studies, - partners must be honest, accurate, and transparent when reporting their findings, - partners must protect the privacy and confidentiality of individuals or organizations involved in the WP, - partners must ensure that data is collected, stored, and shared in a secure and anonymized manner, - partners should disclose any potential conflicts of interest that could influence the design, conduct, or reporting of their research, - partners must respect intellectual property rights, including patents, copyrights, and trade secrets, while appropriately crediting and citing the work of others.
5. Have you considered any gender issues in the work?	No
a. Which ones?	No gender issues could be envisioned in the writing of the screening guidelines. Using and applying the guidelines and technologies described is gender neutral.
b. How did they affect the work and/ or results?	N/A
6. What kind of open science actions have you included in the work and results?	Primarily the results and conditions of Deliverable 2.3 are intended to be used for improvement of internal protocols and for scientific work related to gene editing and

	screening and molecular characterization of gene edited plant material. Improved protocols and workflows can be made open access via publications or availability on public platforms.
7. In this Deliverable/ Milestone, what kind of governance/ regulation issues do you foresee?	This deliverable report may be interesting for regulatory entities, such as EFSA, European Commission. But no problems are foreseen.
a. What kind of change to a product-based regulatory system could enable its wider acceptance by taking into account	N/A
i. the development stage of the product,	N/A
ii. its benefits and risks, and	N/A
iii. its degree of certainty about its future properties.	N/A